

RISK OF BIAS				APPLICABILITY CONCERNS			
Study	Patient Selection	Index Test	Reference Standard	Flow and Timing	Patient Selection	Index Test	Reference Standard
Neonatal							
<i>Adib 2012</i>	☹️	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
<i>Bender 2008</i>	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
<i>Bonac 2000</i>	😐	😊	😐	😊	😊	😊	😊
<i>Boo 2008</i>	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
<i>Groselj- Grenc 2009</i>	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
<i>Guibourdenche 2002</i>	😞	😊	😐	😊	😊	😊	😊
<i>Koskenvuo 2003</i>	😐	😊	😐	😊	😊	😊	😊
<i>Lopez Sastre 2006</i>	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
<i>Naher 2011</i>	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
<i>Resch 2003</i>	😊	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊
<i>Sakha 2008</i>	😐	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
<i>Schlapbach 2013</i>	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
<i>Vazzalwar 2004</i>	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
<i>Zahedpasha 2009</i>	😐	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊
Paediatric							
<i>Calò Carducci 2014</i>	😊	😊	😐	😊	😊	😊	😊
<i>Groselj- Grenc 2009</i>	😊	😊	😞	😊	😊	😊	😊
<i>Pourakbari 2010</i>	😐	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😐
<i>Simon 2008</i>	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊	😊